

MEDICINAL PREPARATION OF BENZOCAINE AND FORMULATION OF NANOGEL FROM BENZOCAINE FOR GETTING ANALGESIC ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

- The ethyl ester of p-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) is benzocaine. It can be made by reducing ethyl p-nitrobenzoate or by Fischer esterification from PABA and ethanol.^[1]
- Benzocaine is a local anesthetic that is frequently used as cough drops or as a topical pain treatment. Many over-the-counter anesthetic ointments, including those for oral ulcers, contain it as their active component.^[2]
- The goal of this research was to create a novel benzocaine gel with improved properties appropriate for local anesthetic activity. Drug penetration improved when the benzocaine content in HPMC gels was raised to 15%, but only a little rise was observed beyond that.^[3]
- Local anesthetics such as benzocaine are more effective when administered using nanogel-based delivery methods,

which use nanogels—tiny particles in the gel—to distribute drugs optimally. This approach presents a viable way to distribute drugs in a focused and efficient manner.^[4]

- The nanogel was made of a biocompatible polymer, which produced a stable matrix. High drug-loading efficiency and extended release properties were exhibited by the nanogel.^[5]

KEYWORDS: Benzocaine, Nanogel, Carbopol 934.

INTRODUCTION

FIG 1. BENZOCAINE STRUCTURE.

In an effort to find efficient ways to manage pain, several pain-relief formulations have been developed. Benzocaine is a common local anesthetic that has long been a mainstay of pain management because of its exceptional ability to numb specific locations. However, the effectiveness of administration and duration of action of traditional benzocaine formulations are frequently problematic.^[1]

Polymer hydrogels are joined at the nanoscale by chemical and physical cross-linking to produce nanogels. The typical size range of nanogels is between 20 and 200 nm.^[2]

For regulated drug delivery, active drug molecules can be transported using stable nanoparticles called nanogels.^[3]

In recent years, nanogels—three-dimensional, cross-linked polymeric networks at the nanoscale—have drawn a lot of interest for use in drug administration.^[4]

They are appropriate for pharmaceutical usage due to their special qualities, which include good biocompatibility, a substantial drug-loading capacity, and controlled-release characteristics.^[4,5]

Although traditional gels and creams frequently exhibit poor skin penetration and a shorter duration of action, benzocaine, a local anesthetic, is frequently employed in topical formulations.^[5]

Benzocaine formulations based on nanogels have been suggested as a way to get around these restrictions. These formulations may improve penetration and prolong anesthetic effects.^[6]

1.] EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

FIG NO. 2 BENZOCAINE.

Benzocaine

An ester-based topical local anesthetic called benzocaine is frequently used to temporarily relieve pain and itching brought on by burns, insect stings, and mild skin irritations. However, it has been connected to methemoglobinemia in youngsters and may cause allergic reactions, particularly in those with damaged skin.

Benzocaine inhibits nerve impulse conduction to provide its local anesthetic action. In order to prevent sodium-ion entrance during depolarization, it binds reversibly to voltage-gated sodium channels in the neuronal cell membrane. This stops action potentials from starting and spreading, which causes a brief lack of feeling at the application site. Due to its low water solubility, benzocaine's effect is limited to the surface, delivering regional anesthetic with minimal systemic dissemination.

Nanogel

What a nanogel is: A nanogel is a nanoscale hydrogel made of networks of cross-linked polymers that can retain medications inside its structure while yet being very biocompatible and water-swallowable.

Introduction to Benzocaine Nanogel

Nanogels provide an efficient topical drug delivery method for benzocaine, improving the anesthetic's solubility, stability, and controlled release.

They also make them perfect for targeted applications including minor skin irritations, bug bites, and burn pain treatment. Benzocaine nanogels offer better penetration and longer-lasting release than traditional gels or ointments.

Benzocaine nanogel offers an efficient and stable formulation for localized pain control by fusing the medicinal qualities of benzocaine with the sophisticated delivery capabilities of nanogels.

OBJECTIVE

To create benzocaine nanogel with appropriate excipients and polymers for a stronger local anesthetic effect.

To assess the drug concentration, viscosity, pH, shape, and particle size of the created nanogel.

To assess the in vitro drug release profile in order to guarantee sustained and regulated release.

To evaluate the mucoadhesive qualities for extended oral cavity retention.

To assess how well benzocaine nanogel and traditional benzocaine gels relieve pain.

CHARACTERIZATION OF BENZOCAINE NANOGEL.**TABLE NO. 1**

Parameter	Method / instrument
Particle size & distribution	Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)
Zeta potential	Zeta sizer
Morphology	SEM / TEM
Viscosity & rheology	Viscometer
Ph measurement	Ph meter
Drug loading and encapsulation efficiency	UV visible spectroscopy
In vitro drug release	Diffusion cell / Membrane
Stability studies	Storage under V conditions

Advantages in drug delivery

Enhance permeation of poorly soluble drugs like benzocaine

Protect drugs from degradation

Provide localized and prolonged therapeutic effect

Reduce side effects compared to conventional formulations

FIG 3: BENZOCAINE NANOGEL FORMULATION.

Role of UV visible spectroscopy in benzocaine nanogel

TABLE NO. 2

Aspect	Details
Principle	Based on Beer–Lambert law; absorbance is directly proportional to the concentration.
λ_{max} (wavelength of maximum absorbance)	~285–290 nm (depending on solvent).
Applications	- Drug loading and encapsulation efficiency: measures <u>untrapped drug</u> in supernatant → drug content. - Release studies: monitors cumulative release during in-vitro diffusion.
Stability testing	<u>detects</u> degradation or changes in drug spectrum.
Advantages	Simple, rapid, and non-destructive; minimal sample preparation; accurate and reproducible quantification.

FIG 4 UV SPECTRA OF BENZOCAINE

Fig no 04: UV Spectra of Benzocaine.

CONCLUSION

Benzocaine nanogel effectively blends effectiveness, stability, safety, and improved topical application, making it a better option compared to older formulations. Future research looking into real-world testing, large-scale manufacturing, and mixing with other numbing agents can help improve its use in clinical settings and increase its potential for treating various conditions.

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